

**RESIDUAL LIFE ESTIMATION OF CORRODED CRITICAL PIPING
USING PROBABILISTIC AND STATISTICAL METHODS**

EG5906 Individual Project in Safety and Reliability Engineering for Oil & Gas

by

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ABSTRACT

Oil and gas piping systems are subject to corrosion that can reduce wall thickness. Given the importance of the piping system for connecting components within a plant or reservoir and transporting fluids, the failure of such a sensitive system will result in a high-hazard consequence. Hence, adequate inspection, repair, and maintenance of the piping system are required. However, not all inspection, repair, and maintenance processes are efficient and cost-effective; therefore, it would be helpful to estimate the residual life of the piping systems using several methods and compare the results to assess each technique's conservatism. This study aims to evaluate the residual life of a corroded piping system using different approaches with similar wall-thickness data, compare solutions from the various methods, and identify the advantages and disadvantages of each technique. Evaluate the minimum data required to comfortably predict wall thickness reduction in a piping system by investigating and reviewing related studies. The United Kingdom Health and Safety Executive (HSE) highlighted the need for an efficient, cost-saving process for estimating the remaining wall thickness of a corroded metal surface, recommending statistical methods and computer-aided tools. This study applied statistical analysis of sixteen (16) year wall thickness measurements from an oil and gas piping system using Reliasoft's Weibull++ tool and compared the results with conventional industry methods. The application of the computer-aided tool makes the statistical extreme value analysis easier and efficient. The study revealed that extreme-value statistical analysis addresses the uncertainties associated with the data. It is a practical and conservative means of determining the remaining life of corroded piping. The extreme value statistical method provides a probabilistic perspective on the current state of the piping system, accounting for the entire system/line. However, all the techniques can produce reliable results if a large amount of data with lower uncertainty is available.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Chapter 1:	Introduction.....	1
1.1	Background.....	1
1.2	Aim and Objectives	2
1.3	Scope	2
1.4	Project Format	3
Chapter 2:	Literature Review.....	4
2.1	Piping Management.....	4
2.1.1	Piping Wall Thickness Measurement with NDE.....	4
2.2	Common Types of Corrosion Affected by an Oil and Gas Facility.....	5
2.3	Residual Life of a Piping System	5
2.4	Summary and Conclusion.....	14
Chapter 3	Degradation and Life Data Analysis.....	16
3.1	Uncertainties Associated with Inspection Data	16
3.1.1	Data Collection	16
3.2	Material.....	17
3.2.1	Piping in a Water Injection System.....	17
3.2.2	Measuring tool	17
3.2.3	Weibull ++	17
3.3	Methodology.....	17
3.3.1	API 510 Semi-Quantitative and API 570 Point-to-Point Methods.....	17
3.3.2	Degradation Analysis	18
3.3.3	Life Data Analysis.....	19
3.4	Comparison between the API 570 Linear Extrapolation and Degradation Model Analysis Approach with the Reliasoft Weibull ++ Statistical tool.....	22
Chapter 4:	Residual life estimation. Life data, Degradation model applications, and Point-to-Point Analysis.....	23
4.1	Case study: Piping in an oil and gas water injection system.....	23
4.2	Point-to-Point Analysis.....	23
4.3	Degradation Model Analysis	24
4.4	Life Data Analysis	26
4.4.1	Comparison between Reliasoft Weibull++ and Relyence Weibull Life Data Analysis	27
4.4.2	Reliability Analysis.....	29
4.4.3	Percentile Life.....	29
4.4.5	Model Fitting.....	30
4.5	Preferences and Limitations of the Methods used in Estimating Residual Wall Thickness and Life of Oil and Gas Piping.....	35
Chapter 5	Conclusions and Recommendations.....	38
5.1	Conclusion.....	38
5.2	Recommendations for Further Studies.....	39

REFERENCES 43

APPENDICES 48

LIST OF TABLES

2.1	Results for Gumbel and Weibull Extreme Value analysis with Weibull++ tool.	8
2.2.	Result of Probabilistic analysis of a corroded wellhead casing system [33]	10
2.3.	Results obtained for the Degradation Power Model using Weibull++ tool.	13
3.1.	Tank Wall thickness Measurements	21
4.1	API510 Semi-Quantitative Analysis of Residual Life of Corroded Piping System	23
4.2	Time to Failure Analysis for the Corroded Piping System from Point-to-Point Method.	23
4.3.	Linear Degradation Model Parameters	24
4.4.	Extrapolated time to failure results from the Linear Degradation Model	24
4.5.	Life Data Analysis of Failure Time	26
4.6.	Life Data Analysis Result for Reliasoft Weibull++ and Relyence Weibull.	27
4.7.	Reliability Characteristics of the Water Injection Piping System	29
4.8.	Percentile Life of Piping Sub-System corresponding to Upper and Lower 90 % Confidence Bounds	29
4.9.	2P-Weibull Distribution parameters	30
4.10.	Gumbel Extreme Value Estimation of Minimum Wall Thickness with Reliasoft Weibull++	35
4.11.	Comparison of Time to failure (Day) for Point-to-Point vs Life Data Analysis	35

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure	Page
2.1. Assumed Finite Element Model of corroded Piping Section in a Water Injection System (Adapted from [17])	6
2.2. Fitted Gaussian Distribution for measured pipe wall thickness (Adapted from [2])	7
2.3. Normal Cumulative Distribution Curve (Adapted from [2])	8
3.1. Water Injection Pipeline System (Adapted and modified from [51])	16
3.2. Sample Area divided into Blocks (Adapted and modified from [19])	17
3.3. A typical Exponential Model Degradation vs Time graph	19
4.1. Degradation Time Graph (Linear)	25
4.2. Degradation Time Graph (Logarithm)	26
4.3. Residual Life and Degradation Time Graph (Linear)	26
4.4. Probability Density Function for the Reliasoft Weibull++ software tool.	28
4.5. Probability Density Function (PDF) for Relyence Weibull software tool.	29
4.6. Gumbel Probability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.	32
4.7. Weibull Probability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.	33
4.8. Gumbel Reliability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.	33
4.9. Weibull Reliability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.	34

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND NOTATIONS

MAH	Major Accident Hazard
API	American Petroleum Institute
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
H ₂ S	Hydrogen Sulfide
UK HSE	United Kingdom Health Safety and Executives
FORM	First-Order Reliability Method
SORM	Second-Order Reliability Method
MCS	Monte Carlo Simulation
HAZID	Hazard Identification
HAZOP	Hazard and Operability
NDE	Non-Destructive Examination
CML	Condition Monitoring Location
TML	Thickness Monitoring Location
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
PDF	Probability Density Function
QCP	Quick Calculation Pad
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
u	Location Parameter for Gumbel Distribution
$f(x)$	Probability Density Function (PDF)
$R(x)$	Reliability Function,
1P	One-parameter Distribution
2P	Two-Parameter Distribution
3P	Three-Parameter Distribution
STCR	Short Term Corrosion Rate
LTCR	Long Term Corrosion Rate
CR	Corrosion Rate
LK Value	Likelihood Value

MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimation
F	Failure
S	Suspension/Safe
x	Wall Thickness
t	Time
PF	Probability of Failure
EVA	Extreme Value Analysis
ALARP	As Low As Reasonably Practicable
N	Total length of CML
F_t	Temperature Rating Factor
E_w	The efficiency of the Welded Joint
D	External Pipeline Diameter
d	Depth of Metal Loss on Pipeline Surface
P_d	Design Pressure of the Pipeline
a, b	Degradation Model Parameters
QRA	Quantitative Risk Analysis
MTTF	Mean Time to Failure
σ_Y	Yield Strength of the Metal Pipeline
ρ^2	Variance
ρ	Coefficient of Correlation
$\lambda(x)$	Failure Rate Function,
β_2	Shape Parameter for Weibull Distribution
η	Scale Parameter Distribution
γ	Location Parameter
β_1	Scale Parameter for Gumbel Distribution
μ_x	Mean
σ_x	Standard Deviation
η_u	Usage Factor (0.72 for pipelines)

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

Piping refers to the cylindrical connections inside the boundaries of a process plant connecting various components and used to transport hydrocarbons in the oil and gas industry from one part of the plant to another. Piping systems in the oil and gas industry have experienced numerous failures due to corrosion, leading to loss of containment, fires and explosions, environmental degradation, and lost production time. To safeguard the integrity of oil and gas piping systems at all times of operation, maintenance should follow efficient approaches and standards. As the piping system ages, its integrity deteriorates, and its failure probability increases. Researchers have established that the most significant factor in oil and gas facility failures is corrosion; hence, the assessment and determination of its effects on these systems should be given due attention to reduce future failures, which would have significant consequences for the asset, personnel, and the environment. An exemplary Major Accident Hazard (MAH) in which poor asset management led to loss of containment, loss of personnel, environmental degradation, and the sudden deaths of workers occurred on 3 December 1984, at a Union Carbide Pesticide plant in Bhopal, Central India. Due to several of this type of accident occurring worldwide, regulatory bodies have developed specific guidelines to ensure asset safety.

The API Piping inspection code is one such code implemented to help manage the safety of an oil and gas facility, specifically piping. The API 570, Piping Inspection Code, mandated the following processes to enhance piping integrity in the oil and gas industry: development of corrosion rate data for piping systems, monitoring, and inspection interval, investigation of pipe wall thickness, alteration of the piping system and review of the performance of oil and gas piping in plants, etc. The energy sector continues to shift towards risk-based, data-driven methods to support better decisions on integrity and equipment suitability for operation. Predicting residual wall thickness and residual life for critical in-service piping systems is an essential top priority in the oil and gas sector to reduce the financial burden of inspection, maintenance, and piping failure in harsh environments or other factors that promote corrosion. For the petroleum and chemical processing industries, the widely used API 570, Piping Inspection Code, sets out conditions and recommendations required to maintain the structural integrity of installed oil and gas piping systems. The specifications include the suitability of the equipment to perform their designated function and a risk-based inspection approach to investigating piping experiencing corrosion, high pressure, and components subjected to mechanical stresses, including methods for assessing reductions in pipe wall thickness.

API 570 [1] recommends that operators using metal piping to distribute petroleum products adopt the following approach to evaluate corrosion rates: point-to-point methods and a statistical approach. It seems to be a crucial subject for asset managers, as it determines how realistically wall thickness and residual life can be reliably estimated to effectively manage hazards and reduce the level of loss of containment due to corrosion. However, most piping systems are complex, and most methods used to inspect their reliability are financially inflated for companies. Different industry standards are used depending on the nature of the system, and the concept of corrosion modelling applies to any such approach. In any case, the ability to measure wall thickness varies, e.g., pigging for pipelines and manual NDE methods for piping systems on an installation. In piping systems within installations, such as water injection piping, pigging cannot be utilised; hence, NDE techniques are used to evaluate the measured wall thickness as best as possible.

Due to the irregularities and uncertainties associated with corrosion, various methods have not been considered highly realistic for analysing corrosion data. Hence, it is relevant for companies to adopt a cost-effective approach and an efficient means of predicting piping failure. The use of statistical extreme-value and point-to-point methods for analysing corrosion inspection data is essential, and validating these approaches for estimating the residual life of a corroded facility is also vital [2]. Although the statistical extreme value techniques have also been recommended in several academic studies and reports, an apparent lack of awareness and a perception that these methods are somewhat abstract have limited their application.

Sophisticated computer tools should be developed to enhance further the efficiency and simplicity of using a statistical approach to evaluate the remaining wall thickness of a piping system [2]. The development of the Reliasoft Weibull++ software addresses part of the problem identified by the UK HSE; however, it would be appropriate to also test its efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and accuracy by comparing its results with those from commonly used methods such as point-to-point and degradation techniques.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

This project aims to identify and compare various known approaches, measure their uncertainties and weaknesses by analysing real data using the Reliasoft Weibull++ software, and provide feasible recommendations for future analyses to asset managers to ensure quality decision-making during operations.

To achieve the aim, the project's specific objectives are:

- Review literature related to estimating wall thickness methods, including the point-to-point methods, non-destructive parametric degradation models, and statistical minimum extreme value distribution methods.
- Assess the minimum information and data requirements needed to predict wall thickness with confidence, including the relationships between the number and quality of inspection points and the inspection area coverage.
- Assess and compare techniques via a case study using real data, carried out using the Reliasoft Weibull++ software analysis tool, where possible, and demonstrate the benefits and constraints of each approach.
- Describe the benefits, constraints, and uncertainties associated with each approach and develop a list of recommendations for analysts carrying out this type of study.

1.3 Scope

This research will be centred on the estimation of residual life and remaining wall thickness of oil and gas piping exposed to moisture and corrosion-causing agents such as CO₂ and H₂S. Various approved methods, including the point-to-point method and the statistical analysis approach, will be reviewed based on their efficacy, cost-effectiveness, and risk level. Results from analysing field data using the Reliasoft Weibull++ software will be compared with API-approved methods to determine a suitable piping inspection interval and an integrity management plan. This study focuses on the most significant defect (the thinnest wall thickness expected or measured across the inspection area during inspection as a random variable. Most reviews in the study are cited from pipelines and not specifically for piping units in a water injection system. However, the approach of estimating the residual life of a corroded metal does not change for any facility with internal corrosion. The study considers only the minimum extreme values in statistical extreme value analysis.

However, this study does not consider factors such as the metal's chemical composition or metallurgical variations, the harshness of the environment, or the pressure in the piping section, which influence metal loss. Also, the consequences of failure and the risk assessment of the possible failure are not considered in this study.

1.4 Project Format

This project consists of five (5) chapters. It is organised as follows: Chapter 2 highlights the importance of oil and gas piping management and the available methods for evaluating the remaining life of a piping system affected by corrosion. Chapter 3 discusses the piping system materials in the project and the tools used to assess wall thicknesses. The study's approach to data extraction was also discussed, along with the associated uncertainties. However, limited work has been done on uncertainty because it is outside the study framework. Chapter 4 presents results and discussions of reliability characteristics, including MTTF, failure rate, reliability, and probability of failure. Probability plots were fitted and compared to determine what distribution best describes the data in the study, and an analysis on percentile life considering different bounds was emphasised. Also included in this session is a discussion of the results of extreme-value analysis used to determine the minimum wall thickness of a corroded surface. The results from various methods were adequately compared and deliberated. Lastly, based on the study's reviews and results, conclusions were drawn regarding the integrity of the corroded piping sampled and the data used in the study. Recommendations were provided based on the findings in this study and from a review of previous research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

At the end of this chapter, the reader should understand the meaning of piping management and its need for accurate decision-making to enhance the integrity of a piping system, reduce failures due to corrosion, and confidently specify inspection, repair, and maintenance intervals. At any given time in the service of an oil and gas piping system, the asset manager must understand the facility's remaining useful life to help reduce failures and their consequences. Therefore, a review of residual life and the methods used to estimate it for piping systems has been conducted, highlighting the strengths of each technique.

Given the cost and technical requirements for thoroughly inspecting an oil and gas piping system with minimal access, the entire system is not continuously sampled during inspection. The accessibility of a piping system will determine which approach or device to use during its inspection. This research will discuss which method is appropriate for inspecting an inaccessible piping system. However, there is a need for approaches such as extreme-value analysis to determine the minimum data required for the piping integrity assessment. Several sophisticated computer tools, such as the Reliasoft Weibull++, which uses statistical analysis to address data scarcity by estimating the minimum possible value, have been developed and will be demonstrated using real-life data in this chapter. Also, reliability analysis using advanced FORM, SORM, and Crude Monte Carlo simulation will be performed with a computer-aided reliability tool (Strurel/Comrel) to assess the integrity (probability of failure and reliability) of a pipeline with a wall thickness below the nominal wall thickness.

2.1 Piping Management

Piping management involves recommending suitable piping inspection approaches, evaluation of components liable to be affected by hazards such as corrosion, identifying hazard-causing agents and consequences of accidents caused by such agents through HAZOP or HAZID study, and designating repair strategies to help lessen the probability of a piping system failing and the consequences of failure [3]. As stated in [4], approximately 25% of oil and gas facility wrecks are due to corrosion, and since an exact solution to preventing corrosion entirely has not been discovered, the need to investigate corrosion, specify the inspection schedule, and correctly specify preventive measures before such failures occur is vital.

2.1.1 Piping Wall Thickness Measurement with NDE

Conditions where piping is inaccessible for massive pigging, the Non-Destructive Examination (NDE) approach is highly preferable for evaluating piping wall thickness at condition monitoring locations (CMLs) or other predetermined locations. Wall thickness evaluation is the predominant type of Non-Destructive Examination carried out on the internal and external surfaces of piping systems in the oil & gas and petrochemical industries. However, the effectiveness of this process depends on the sophistication of the device used and the corrosion configuration [5]. There are already complex pigging inspection techniques used to assess pipe wall thickness, but for smaller process piping where pigging cannot be used, manual NDE techniques must be adopted.

2.2 Common Types of Corrosion Affected by an Oil and Gas Facility

Several types of corrosion occur in the metals used in the oil and gas industry; however, the specific forms of corrosion are H₂S corrosion (sour corrosion), CO₂ corrosion (sweet corrosion), SO₂ corrosion, etc. Sweet and sour corrosion predominantly occurs in the oil and gas industry and is the most widely studied corrosion [6, 7]. Researchers have continuously studied the mechanisms of CO₂ and H₂S corrosion, though it remains unclear whether the mechanisms are universal across all metals, as they depend on factors that influence corrosion [8, 9]. Sweet corrosion occurs at the inner and outer surfaces of the pipe when CO₂ present in the hydrocarbon reacts with water, forming an acidic oxide that reacts with other iron to initiate corrosion. Whereas sour corrosion occurs in localised patterns, making it very difficult to detect during inspection. They are developed when H₂S is present at approximately 100 ppm or more within a piping system or its environment. Sour corrosion results in pitting on the pipe surface [10].

2.3 Residual Life of a Piping System

The residual life of an asset is the piping's life span, measured from the date it began transporting hydrocarbons to the end of its useful life. The RUL estimation helps integrity engineers decide on the next inspection and the time required to repair or replace an asset's components. Due to continuous use of pipes, corrosion affects capacity, safety, and pressure containment, and consequently, the reliability of pipeline systems.

However, researchers and oil and gas operating companies have developed computer models and probabilistic approaches that are more efficient and cost-effective, and that pose a low level of risk when used. Irrespective of the positive characteristics of these media, it would be more reasonable for any adopted approach to yield a reliable result to avoid a hazard. Also, an inaccurate determination of the inline inspection interval would result in excessive spending. To conclude on which method is best, the subsection below provides a review of the various approaches to estimating the residual life of a corroded piping system. The residual life is given mathematically as;

$$Residual\ Life = \frac{Current\ Thickness - Minimum\ Thickness}{Corrosion\ Rate\ (\frac{mm}{yr})} \quad (2.1)$$

2.3.1 Methods of Predicting Residual Life of Metal Piping

Several methods have been developed to determine the residual life of corroded piping; however, none is free of disadvantages, despite their apparent advantages [11]. The risk-based inspection process should be part of a comprehensive approach to enhancing the integrity of the installation's facilities and technologies. Its objective is to make strategic decisions on resource optimisation to mitigate the consequences of accidents arising from failures of critical parts of an installation. The inspection plan can then target high-risk equipment and be designed to detect potential degradation before it threatens wellness-for-service. Delphi, HAZOP, and HAZID are examples of a risk-based inspection approach.

HAZOP and Delphi methods incorporate the ideas and experiences of professionals in the study of pipe degradation and can be used to estimate pipeline integrity. A survey of 30 parameters was conducted to understand their influence on pipeline degradation and to rank them by their capacity to drive deterioration. It was concluded that the Delphi approach to pipeline degradation is a risk-based inspection method that supports asset managers' decision-making. Although this method is a rule-of-thumb approach that can be considered unreliable for specific reasons, such as the level of the

participant's expertise or the clarity of the task, it can also incur high costs due to incorrect assumptions or ideology [12]. To avoid the risk-based inspection methodologies (HAZOP or Delphi) described above, several methods were established, including the Point-to-point method used in API 570 [1], Non-Destructive Parametric statistical models, Statistical, and Probabilistic approaches.

2.3.1.1 Point-to-Point Method

A comparative study between the point-to-point and application of degradable models in the analysis of corrosion data further showed that degradation models are more conservative than the API 570 point-to-point approach, potentially leading to excessive spending if adopted for decision-making [13]. Some researchers, including Kasai et al. [14], have applied the point-to-point method to predict the depth of corrosion on a metal vessel. To reduce the uncertainty in this method, it was combined with the extreme value analysis.

This approach is only suitable for uniform corrosion, where the growth rate is constant across the pipeline surface. The linear corrosion growth rate model is a deterministic model that uses point data from the pipeline surface. The model is used to evaluate pipeline wall thickness over time, assuming corrosion behaviour is linear and constant [15].

2.3.1.2 Statistical Extreme Value Approach

This approach is used to analyse historical data on an asset and has been applied across several fields, including finance and engineering. In this method, sets of maximum or minimum data are extrapolated from the entire historical failure data collected from a system and fitted to various statistical models, including normal, lognormal, Gumbel, and Weibull. These models generate probabilistic plots that explain the data sets and can be used to predict future failures in the system. Extreme-value statistical analysis enables an asset manager to systematically evaluate the reliability of a corroded facility using extreme corrosion data. Extreme-value statistical analysis is more rewarding when applied to localised corrosion, which is prevalent in the oil and gas industry.

However, different forms of corrosion would require separate statistical analyses to improve the accuracy of the results. When defects are uniform, it is best to estimate the remaining wall thickness of the pipe using statistical regression analysis or the point extrapolation technique, assuming corrosion growth is constant across the piping surface. This method is suitable for a water transmission metal pipeline with uniform corrosion [16].

A typical procedure of statistical method in estimating pipe wall thickness/residual wall thickness of metal piping is explained below using data from section (4.1) of the UK HSE report [2];

- A segment or portion of the pipe could be sampled for the entire piping network where access is not provided, or adequate time to carry out a full inspection over the whole piping network system is not provided.

Figure 2.1. Assumed Finite Element Model of corroded Piping Section in a Water Injection System (Adapted from [17])

- The inspection data are arranged in increasing order and grouped into different defect ranges at equal intervals (frequency). The consolidated data are plotted against their respective frequencies to form a frequency distribution curve, as shown in Fig. 2.2.
- The frequency distribution curve is converted into a mathematical form that fits the data accurately to obtain a reliable result. When the wrong distribution is chosen for a set of inspection data, the results of such an investigation tend to be unrealistic. A simple method for fitting corrosion data is to normalise the data by dividing the distribution (frequency) by the total number of data points. However, not all corrosion data follow a normal distribution, and studies have shown that other distributions better capture non-uniform (electrochemical influence) corrosion. Fig. 2.2 shows the fitted data set, which follows a normal distribution, and can be used to visualise whether the assumed distribution clarifies the nature of the corrosion defect on the pipe.

Figure 2.2. Fitted Gaussian Distribution for measured pipe wall thickness (Adapted from [2])

From the normal distribution curve in Fig. 2.2, the mean and standard deviation of the parameter are derived, allowing the pipe wall thickness to be evaluated. Although this might be complex, it can also be assessed by plotting the cumulative distribution function (CDF) curve in Fig. 2.3, the Gaussian statistical distribution Eq. (2.2), using the same group of data, and the proportion of the pipe wall thickness less than the minimum pipe thickness from the inspection data would be derived. The minimum value at which leakage from the pipe would occur can be determined through this process.

$$F(x) = \int_{\alpha}^x f(x)dx = \int_{\alpha}^x \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}, \quad (2.2)$$

Another approach to fitting corrosion data is the survival function, $S(x)$, which is the probability that the pipe wall thickness does not reduce more than an established minimum pipe wall thickness, x , mathematically the survivor function is stated as;

$$S(x) = P[X > x] = 1 - F(x) \quad (2.3).$$

Figure 2.3. Standard Cumulative Distribution Curve (Adapted from [2])

Although the extreme value procedure is ideal, it has some drawbacks due to the amount of data available. When adequate data (100%) is available, Poisson, Gaussian, or lognormal distribution may be preferred. However, in the field, the possibility of (100%) data being available is low and would be expensive and time-consuming to gather. Given the different corrosion degradation mechanisms on a piping surface, it is erroneous to fit all corrosion data to a Gaussian or Poisson distribution; hence, a specific distribution is required [18]. Some distributions suitable for fitting non-uniform corrosion and inspection data with inadequate information have been derived. An example of such is the extreme value distribution.

Extreme Value Statistical Methods

Extreme value analysis is a statistical method used to estimate a system's probability of failure or a component's (e.g., wall thickness) worst condition, based on certain assumptions and observed/measured data. Extreme value analysis offers an alternative technique for evaluating minimum pipe thickness, particularly when the distribution of corrosion is uncertain and ample historical data on corrosion is available [19].

The findings in [9] can be validated by demonstrating the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool's capacity to perform extreme-value statistical analysis to evaluate the minimum wall thickness for a piping system, using the data set from section (6) of the UK HSE report [2].

Case study: Evaluation of Minimum Wall Thickness Using Extreme Value technique in Weibull++.

Given the total length of metal surface investigated as 1250mm (N), to compute the ordinate from the relationship as follows;

$$Ordinate = \left[1 - \left(\frac{N}{1+N} \right) \right] \times 100\%, \quad (2.4)$$

Applying Eq. (2.4), the ordinate is calculated as 0.08%, and the minimum thickness of the piping is 1.8mm with a one-sided 95% lower confidence limit of 1.2mm, approximately as computed from the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool using the Gumbel distribution.

Table 2.1. Results for Gumbel and Weibull Extreme Value analysis with the Weibull++ tool.

Report Type	Weibull++ QCP	
	Gumbel Distribution	Weibull Distribution
BX% Life At	0.08	0.08
Confidence Bounds Used	1-Sided	1-Sided
Confidence Bounds Method	Fisher Matrix	Fisher Matrix
Confidence Level	0.9	0.9
Weibull++ Output		
B0.08% Life	1.8mm	2.7 mm
Lower Bound (0.1)	1.2mm	2.5

Based on the minimum thickness results from the Weibull++ tool (Table 2.1), the Gumbel distribution is more conservative, with a minimum thickness of 1.8mm. In comparison, the 3P-Weibull distribution has a minimum thickness of 2.7mm and an approximate one-sided 95% lower confidence limit of 2.5. This is not arguable because Eq. (2.4) was developed based on the Gumbel distribution, not the Weibull distribution, though it can still be used for both models. However, in some localised metal-corrosion studies, the Weibull distribution is the best fit for the corrosion data, though this depends on the metal grade [20]. The idea of fitting the corrosion data is to give the analyst a sense of the parameter before implementing the model in the analysis, thereby reducing the complexity of using rigorous models and algorithms, as in [21]. A document issued by the UK Health and Safety Executive studied this technique and stated that valid statistical approaches are available; however, engineers or regulatory organisations should focus on developing computational methods to improve their efficacy and minimise the effects of uncertainties when applied.

When using the statistical regression method, care should be taken to avoid bias in data treatment, given uncertainties in pipe thickness measurements arising from the measuring tool, human factors, and material property variations [22]. However, such an approach is suitable for uniform corrosion, where the corrosion rate is constant throughout the pipe surface. Dealing with non-uniform corrosion rates requires an absolute method to achieve a reliable result. Extreme value statistics is an appropriate approach for examining localised/non-uniform corrosion data; [23] used it to determine the maximum pit depth over the surface area of a metallic oil tube.

A study of corrosion inspection data used a linear regression model to predict thickness reduction in an oil pipeline, assuming a constant growth rate across the surface. The study found that uncertainties in corrosion data and the assumption of uniform corrosion across an electrochemical process are sources of error, rendering the results unreliable [24]. The pitting corrosion depth of a long pipeline can be confidently analysed to establish inspection time using the extreme value approach [25]. A combination of extreme-value and other parametric methods would be an excellent approach for predicting the maximum corrosion depth [14]. The suitability of the Gumbel distribution, the Weibull distribution, and the Crude Monte Carlo simulation model has been verified for localised corrosion analysis and modelling of pitting corrosion using the statistical extreme value technique, and it was effective in determining future localised corrosion depth. [26-28]. A comprehensive study was conducted in [29] using the Frechet distribution, another form of Extreme value distribution comparable to the Gumbel distribution, by methods of a Gaussian random logarithmic modelling. The investigation revealed that the Weibull distribution is a more suitable method for estimating pitting corrosion in pipelines. Hence, this finding disproves the statement in [21, 28 and 30]. Some Extreme Value methods used in corrosion analysis are: (Fetlcher, Gumbel, Weibull Distributions, etc). The results for the Gaussian and

exponential distributions depend on the number of points sampled and the geometry of the area from which they were measured. A study shows that a large sampling population and high-quality sample collection yield appreciable results in curve fitting. This can also be confirmed in [31].

2.3.1.3 Probabilistic Approach

In engineering practice, several uncertainties are met during the design, construction, maintenance, and inspection of a system. In the probabilistic method, sources of uncertainty, such as skill deficiencies, poor material properties, load variations, and uncommon failure modes, are accounted for in the model, and the system's integrity is assessed by specifying the failure condition. Probabilistic analysis of corroded metal failure under different failure conditions, such as burst pressure and minimum or maximum pipe wall thickness, has been studied by various authors and organisations over the last decade. A commonly used probabilistic method is the limit-state function approach, which defines the condition under which a system fails. A model is developed that includes the stochastic variables responsible for failure, and the model is analysed using a computer-aided reliability tool or algorithms such as Monte Carlo simulation and First- and Second-Order Reliability Methods (FORM/SORM).

The limit state function of corrosion depth d exceeding allowable pipeline thickness $d_{Allowable}$ is given as;

$$G(d_{Allowable}, d, t) = d_{Allowable}(t) - d_{Minimum}(t), \quad (2.9)$$

$$P(t) = P[G(d_{Allowable}, d, t) \leq 0] = P[d(t) \geq d_{Allowable}(t)], \quad (2.10)$$

where d is the reduction in wall thickness due to corrosion (mm), d_{Max} is the allowable pipe wall thickness, t is the time taken for the wall thickness to reduce (years).

The DNV model considers some vital parameters in the model to evaluate pipeline thickness using a probabilistic approach, as shown below;

$$G(t_{Norminal Thickness}, d) = t_{Norminal Thickness} - d, \quad (2.11)$$

$$t_{Norminal Thickness} = \frac{P_d D}{2E_w \eta_u \sigma_Y F_t}, \quad (2.12)$$

$$G(t_{Norminal Thickness}, d) = \frac{P_d D}{2E_w \eta_u \sigma_Y F_t} - d, \quad (2.13)$$

where, F_t is the temperature rating factor, η_u is the usage factor (0.72 for pipelines), σ_Y is the yield strength of the metal pipeline, E_w is the efficiency of the welded joint, D is the external pipeline diameter, d is the depth of metal loss on the pipeline surface, and P_d is the pipeline's design pressure.

Case Study: Table 2.2 presents data from [32] and applies the FORM, SORM, and Crude Monte Carlo probabilistic analysis methods to determine the probability of the pipeline failing at a thickness below the acceptable minimum.

The corrosion data were all distributed and fitted accordingly to determine the best distribution model (normal, lognormal, Gumbel, Weibull). Using Strurel (Comrel) to perform reliability analysis of the pipeline using advanced

FORM, SORM, and MCS methodologies, the results are displayed in Table 2.2. The model utilised the corrosion rate (Q) and the minimum (X_2) and allowable thickness (X_1), respectively. Table 2.2 shows the probability of the pipeline failing using a probabilistic approach. However, the analysis can be used to generate a curve relating the pipeline's service years to the probability or likelihood of failure if a more sophisticated computational tool is used. Such a curve can be used to evaluate pipeline residual life at any given time.

Table 2.2. Result of Probabilistic analysis of a corroded wellhead casing system [33]

Variable	Statistical Distribution	Parameters	Limit State Function	Technique	PF at t =18years
Allowable Thickness (X_1)	Lognormal	$\xi = 0.545, \lambda = 4.3535$	$G(X_1, X_2) = \frac{X_1}{Q} - \frac{X_2}{Q}$	FORM	0.2300
Minimum Thickness (X_2)	Lognormal	$\xi = 0.545, \lambda = 3.7839$		SORM	0.2300
Corrosion Rate (Q)	2P-Weibull	$\beta = 2.1, \eta = 102.3$		MCS	0.2300

Notwithstanding, the result obtained from this model cannot be accepted to a certain degree. The results of the probabilistic analysis can be used to determine the inspection interval and maintenance process to safeguard the pipeline against risk. The results of a probabilistic model are reliable when material properties, geometric and operational parameters, and uncertainties associated with the sizing of corrosion defects are incorporated, as these factors influence the corrosion rate in metals.

A probabilistic model was developed by prioritising the pipe wall thickness, operating pressure and corrosion electric current density to estimate the residual life of the oil pipeline. Statistical analysis of data was performed to determine a suitable distribution for the variables of the model, performing numerical analysis using Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) to assess the probability of the pipeline failing when the pipeline wall thickness reduces, operating pressure exceeds the resistance of the pipeline, or bursting occurs as a result of an increase in crack size [34, 35]. The probabilistic approach of the Crude Monte Carlo simulation technique and the Markov theorem has been widely used to estimate the probability of a pipeline system failing due to corrosion [35, 36]. The findings from this research showed that the combination of both probabilistic approaches (Crude Monte Carlo simulation and Markov modelling) could be a valid means of ensuring pipeline integrity and determining inspection processes [37]. The safety of a pipeline under operating pressure depends on its thickness; if the thickness falls below the design thickness required to withstand the system's maximum operating pressure (MOP), it is likely to burst or leak.

Noor et al. [38] studied the residual life of a corroded pipeline using a semi-probabilistic model based on the standard deviation of inspection data. They compared their findings with a deterministic approach, as in [39]. The DNV approach could be simple to use, but it is not reliable in handling parameter uncertainties. And it does not save costs for an operator, since it requires frequent inspections to obtain reliable information about the system. Also, it is limited to the current condition of the pipeline system. A probabilistic model is the right tool for predicting the pipeline's residual

life (remaining wall thickness or defect depth), as it accounts for uncertainties in the inspection data and provides realistic results.

It was concluded that operating pressure and corrosion defects influence the reliability of the pipeline, and that great attention should be paid to these variables; research should be conducted on the corroded pipeline, considering a single failure mechanism, either reduced wall thickness or increased operating pressure, to attain a reliable result. To further improve the accuracy of results from the corrosion study, inspection data should be distributed with the best model that fits the cumulative curve. For a specific probability of pipeline failure assigned to the pipeline, the required wall thickness for that failure can be directly evaluated from the failure-to-defect-depth probability curve. The remaining life of a corroded pipeline was analysed probabilistically in [40] to quantify the decrease in pipeline integrity under operating pressure and the consequences for the remaining life at a given time during operation. Reliability and sensitivity analyses were conducted on the corroded pipeline to evaluate its integrity and to understand the importance of each variable in the study. Data generated during the inspection were statistically sampled to obtain the best-fitting model, and the results can be considered accurate. The results showed that exposure time, defect depth, and pipeline wall thickness significantly influence the probability of pipeline failure. A non-linear limit-state model was developed, with various variables assumed to be lognormal and normal. Hence, it was concluded that the probabilistic approach to corrosion analysis enables engineers to evaluate the pipeline's reliability index and the probability of failure during operation.

A probabilistic study of a corroded steel pipeline using a stochastic model to predict its residual life due to wall-thickness reduction was conducted in [41]. Failure is inexorable in a pipeline when the load exceeds the resistance, and the pipeline's resistance is significantly dependent on the yield strength, wall thickness, and microstructure of the material. The time-dependent model was used to evaluate the probability of pipeline failure due to metal loss at a given time (years) and to estimate the approximate time required for future inspection or maintenance. A typical corrosion type commonly encountered in the oil and gas industry was analysed in the study. The model was simulated using MCS, and the results were validated as reliable and an alternative means of estimating the residual life of the corroded pipeline. A probabilistic model is an alternative for assessing the integrity of a steel pipeline at any given time, whether in service or out of service. It provides a clear view of the probability of the pipeline failing under increased pressure, reduced pipe wall thickness, or increased corrosion rate. Understanding this condition provides the engineer with a suitable framework for making decisions to avert such risks and schedule maintenance. A probabilistic Bayesian method can be used to accurately measure the likelihood of a steel pipeline failing by leakage or rupture under a given condition. This method can also be used to specify the failure condition or boundary for any size of pipeline system [36]. A precise determination of the residual life of a corroded pipeline over a given period is impossible due to uncertainties arising from measurement and inspection data, and from biased judgments in data treatment [42]. A probabilistic approach can be used to determine the pipeline's failure time, a feature missing from other established methods, such as the point-to-point approach [1]. An illustration was prepared using a pipeline subject to corrosion for 5 years; the time of the pipeline's failure was determined. The corrosion defect was corrected, and the pipeline's reliability increased to 92%. Hence, it was concluded that the probabilistic approach could be replaced by another reliability method that does not estimate pipeline failure time and does not account for uncertainties in inspection data.

Based on the study of Witek et al. [43] on the prediction of pipeline failure using in-line corrosion inspection data, and applying a probabilistic technique. The corrosion growth rate was assumed to be non-linear; statistical mean values for

defect depth and length were used in the non-linear model developed. The model could directly predict the level of metal loss at a given time using the curve. It was stated that the model did not incorporate the imperfection from the inspection tool or process. However, the result from this approach could be exact if the model was developed with the correct assumption that the corrosion growth rate is non-uniform, and if the mean data are used as in [41].

2.3.1.4 Degradation Analysis

This approach begins by defining the level of metal loss that constitutes a piping leak and incorporating this condition into a mathematical model to predict pipe failure over time, using failure data measured at different points on the piping surface subjected to corrosion. The model is used to estimate the system's time-to-failure, and the reliability of the results depends on the quantity of available data. Thus, the technique provides a clear understanding of the corrosion process and the pipeline's residual life, as the model is developed to predict growth rate and time-to-failure (remaining lifetime). In this approach, a model is designed to estimate the time-to-failure and residual-lifetime distributions of the piping system, and analysis is carried out using a degradation model, such as the Weibull++ degradation analysis tool [44]. Some such models are Linear, exponential, power, logarithmic, Gompertz, and Lloyd-Lipow. However, most corrosion mechanisms do not remain uniform over time and appear non-uniform.

Case study: Degradation Analysis based on Exponential Model;

$$d(t) = be^{at}, \quad (2.14)$$

where, $d(t)$ pipe wall thickness at time (t), a and b are model parameters respectively. Both a and b can be evaluated manually or by a computational tool such as Weibull++.

Given that, a and b are 0.00013 and 101.953 respectively in [13], the critical thickness (the point at which leakage is likely to occur) of the pipeline can be evaluated if the year of inspection or the design life is known. The residual wall thickness can be determined directly, assuming a design life of 50 years for the piping.

$$\text{Hence, } d(t) = be^{at}, \quad d(50) = 101.953e^{(0.00013)(50)} = 102.617\text{mm.}$$

Pipe residual thickness after 50 years of operation is 102.617mm. Similarly, knowing the minimum wall thickness of the pipe from the measured data, the pipeline's residual life can be estimated directly from the model, given a Critical degradation thickness of 92 mm.

$d(t) = be^{at}$, $\frac{d(t)}{b} = e^{at}$, taking the natural log of both sides of the equation, we have,

$$t = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{d(t)}{b}\right)}{a}, \quad \text{at } d = 102.617\text{mm, } a \text{ and } b \text{ remains constant, } t = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{92}{101.953}\right)}{0.00013} = 790.18\text{years.}$$

However, this means that no failure can occur in the pipeline before 790.18 years, and, based on the determined time of pipe failure, the inspection interval can be safely specified. The degradation analysis approach is substantially more conservative than the point-to-point method [13].

Exemplifying, from the study in [45], given the Destructive degradation data and inspection time. For a practical degradation analysis, it is expected that the failure condition is predefined; therefore, critical degradation is set to a wall thickness of 3.175mm. Applying the Weibull++ tool's exponential degradation model yields the results shown in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3. Results obtained for the Degradation Power Model using the Weibull++ tool.

Weibull++ QCP Results Report	
B5.78% Life	2649hrs
Lower Bound (0.1)	2406

The total length of the metal surface sample was evaluated as the sum of the individual measurements and was equal to 16.2866mm (N) using Eq. (2.1). The ordinate was 5.78%. At an ordinate of 5.788%, the minimum required for the piping before failure begins is 2649 hrs, and the one-sided 90% lower confidence limit is approximately 2406days, as shown in Table 2.3. From Table 2.3, the degradation line starts exceeding the critical degradation of 3.175 mm at approximately 2792 hours. However, at this point, the system can still perform its duties under normal operating conditions. But it is safer to schedule repair or maintenance before the predicted time.

The above degradation models have been found to be unsuitable for the analysis of localised corrosion, which is predominantly encountered in the oil and gas industry [46]. Hence, researchers have developed suitable parametric models to fill that gap. Examples of such models are: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Bayesian Network, Markov Model, Block-Minima, etc. Although these models have been continuously modified and validated by researchers, they have not been widely adopted by industry for analysing pipeline corrosion to estimate time to failure and the level of pipeline reduction due to corrosion. A qualitative approach to pipeline integrity study was conducted using a dynamic Bayesian network (DBN); the risk of pipeline failure was evaluated as the product of the probability of pipeline failure and the consequences of pipeline failure, expressed as a monetary term (cost). The value of the pipeline failure consequence is estimated from historical pipeline accident costs, and the optimal inspection interval is determined from a utility function curve [47]. Although this method is not exact, the probability of the pipeline failing and its consequences are assumed, leading to an excessive approach due to overestimation. Based on the results in [48], a statistical model was developed to assess the condition of an oil and gas pipeline system during operation using the Artificial Neural Network technique. One of the objectives of their research is to develop a cost-effective, efficient means of analysing pipeline systems under corrosive conditions. The results of this study showed that the corrosion and deterioration of a pipeline could be efficiently analysed using an ANN-based statistical approach. The research of Robert et al. [49] developed a probabilistic finite element model and simulated it using MCS and advanced first- and second-order reliability methods. The reliability index was further used to evaluate the probability of pipeline failure for specific wall thickness and operating pressure, and the results show that the model can be used to comfortably determine the pipeline inspection interval and aid operators in decision-making to enhance safety within their facilities. The findings agree with those of [48, 72].

2.4 Summary and Conclusion

As previously stated, there are no techniques independent of a flaw in the estimation of the residual life of a critical corroded piping system. However, most methods have appreciable biases and cannot be confidently approved for analysing inspection data to assist asset managers in decision-making. Statistical extreme value analysis can be

considered such a method, with its advantages outweighing its limitations. However, a conclusion will be reached if this method also outperforms the other standard methods used in forecasting the remaining life of a corroded metal. In line with the recommendation of HSE 2002 [3], the Weibull++ tool could serve as a gap-filler, providing an efficient and reliable means of analysing the condition of an oil and gas pipeline damaged by corrosion.

The next session of the study will elaborate on the uncertainties associated with corrosion data, methods for collecting corrosion data, the sampled material, methodologies used to analyse corrosion data, and the Weibull++ computer tool used for life data and degradation analysis.

Chapter 3 Degradation and Life Data Analysis

This chapter of the project will discuss the process of extracting wall thickness measurements from a corroded piping surface, a brief highlight of the data quality and the abnormalities associated with the accuracy of the data and the process of obtaining them. Also, the various methodologies reviewed in section 2 of this study will be discussed and tested in this chapter through case studies. The materials, measuring tool, used for measuring the wall thickness of the corroded piping have also been highlighted briefly, and a schematic diagram of a typical reservoir drilling condition identifying the water injection system, comprised of a piping system through which water is injected into the reservoir to enhance oil recovery, has been presented in this chapter.

3.1 Uncertainties Associated with Inspection Data

It is a significant concern for an asset manager to guarantee the safety of oil and gas facilities, and this depends on appropriate decisions taken towards pipeline inspection, repair or maintenance of facilities.

The quality and accuracy of a reliability analysis would rely heavily on the quality of the data available for the study [50]. However, this study does not consider uncertainties arising from the wall thickness-measuring device, the skill of personnel recording the measurement, or other parameters that could affect the measurement quality.

3.1.1 Data Collection

The data used in this study were derived from a water injection system and wall thickness measurements related to internal corrosion degradation of the injection pipe wall. The small diameter of the piping makes it more challenging to observe the degradation mechanism, the shape or depth of corrosion, and therefore requires NDE techniques to evaluate wall thickness and the level of metal loss. An adequate statistical analysis would be conducted using the measured wall thickness. Wall thickness measurements are taken at all four corners of the block (North, East, South, and West). The nominal diameter of the sampled piping is assessed as 8.625 inches (219.075mm), and the nominal wall thickness is 22mm (0.8661 inch).

Figure 3.1. Water Injection Pipeline System (Adapted and modified from [51])

For time, cost, or access reasons, multiple inspections to measure various thicknesses may be prohibitively expensive. Extreme Value Analysis (EVA) primarily concerns the minimum or maximum thickness of an area sampled. The

minimum and maximum thicknesses are used to estimate the distribution's mean and standard deviation. The thickness measurements are extracted from different CML/TMLs or for an individual sample area [52]. Thus, collecting the minimum sample from either a sampled area is always the best choice for estimating the residual life of a corroded facility. The piping system was divided into different segments and CMLs (blocks). Then, the wall thickness is measured at four (4) CML locations, and the minimum value is assumed, as shown in Fig. 3.2. The selected minimum thickness from the individual blocks is incorporated into the Extreme Value model to compute the distribution parameters used in Eq. (3.7-3.13). Whereas, for degradation models, the entire wall thickness measured from each CML/TML is ranked in increasing order of year of measurement before analysis is carried out to obtain the model parameters used in Eq. (3.4-3.6).

Figure 3.2. Sample Area divided into Blocks (Adapted and modified from [19])

3.2 Material

3.2.1 Piping in a Water Injection System

The piping material used in this study is part of a water injection system and is made of Carbon steel.

3.2.2 Measuring tool

A 38DL Plus D-Meter was used to measure wall thickness, with a step-block manual calibration method.

3.2.3 Weibull ++

ReliaSoft Weibull++ is a comprehensive life data analysis and degradation tool used to perform life data and degradation analysis, including multiple distribution models, degradation measurements, or performance data, in a design of experiments geared towards investigating the system's reliability over time.

3.3 Methodology

3.3.1 API 510 Semi-Quantitative and API 570 Point-to-Point Methods.

In the API 510 approach, the remaining life of the corroded piping is evaluated for each Condition Monitoring Location/Thickness Measuring Location (CML/TML). However, this approach may require a consistent assessment of pipes and a high degree of professionalism in estimating the remaining life of the piping.

The following equations are used to estimate the remaining life and corrosion rate of a piping system based on the API 510 method [53];

$$\text{Short-term Corrosion Rate} = \frac{\text{Metal Loss}}{\text{Time Period}} = \frac{T_{\text{Previous}} - T_{\text{last}}}{\text{Time Period}}, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{Long Term Corrosion Rate} = \frac{\text{Metal Loss}}{\text{Time Period}} = \frac{T_{\text{First}} - T_{\text{last}}}{\text{Time Period}}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\text{Residual Life} = \frac{T_{\text{last}} - T_{\text{critical degradation}}}{\text{Corrosion Rate}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where, T_{Last} is the last measured wall thickness, T_{Previous} is the measured wall thickness before the last, T_{First} is the first measured wall thickness, and Time Period is the successive time difference between two inspections. The most significant value obtained from the corrosion rate equations (3.1 and 3.2) is used to estimate the asset's residual life using Eq. (3.3), since it produces the worst condition of the system.

Subsequently, the API 570 approach of Point-to-Point estimation of residual life suggests applying linear extrapolation to predict the residual life of a corroded piping system. In this method, historical data (wall thickness measurements) are collected and plotted as a function of inspection time on a linear graph. The data points are joined by a straight line and extended to future years where wall thickness data are unavailable. Refer to the case study in section (3.4) below for a better understanding of the processes.

3.3.2 Degradation Analysis

Piping degradation is the loss of integrity and performance of a pipeline resulting from ageing, operational conditions, and other factors, such as environmental and human factors, that accelerate deterioration. In forecasting the residual life of a corroded pipeline, it is pertinent for corrosion engineers first to evaluate the rate of degradation relative to the probability of failure, reliability, etc.

The knowledge can then be used to predict the time until the system is likely to fail. Evaluating facility degradation: Using corrosion data to estimate a system's time-to-failure, the degradation factor to be determined should be associated with the system's failure process, and there must be a defined deterioration degree where failure is presumed to have emerged. From the parameters derived from the degradation analysis, an engineer can apply mathematical models directly to estimate the pipeline's remaining thickness, reliability, and failure probability.

The degradation analysis follows the steps below:

- **Step 1:** Adopt the NDE method due to inadequate access for sophisticated pigging devices to go through the Water Injection System.
- **Step 2:** Identifying the section or block of the piping whose wall thickness will be measured.
- **Step 3:** Measure the wall thickness and inspection time at each CML/TML along the piping surface (internal).
- **Step 4:** Choose the degradation model that best fits the set of data and estimate the time to failure, and the reliability characteristics of the piping system due to corrosion.
- **Step 5:** Select the Degradation model wizard, which gives the option to test for the best degradation model.
- **Step 6:** Analyse and implement the best model generated by the software. See Appendices (A.1 and A.2) for a better understanding.
- **Step 7:** Input critical degradation as 500mm and calculate. Check plots and Quick Calculation Pad (QCP) for characteristics of the analysis, including (MTTF, Reliability, Probability of Failure, Failure rate), etc.

Figure 3.3. A typical Exponential Model Degradation vs Time graph

The degradation-time graph in Fig. 3.3 was generated using an exponential model fitted to data from [44]. Graphically, the time to which the system is expected to start failing can be obtained directly from the graph as 2787 hours (8 years) in service. Based on this achievement, the inspection, maintenance, or repair interval can be established.

3.3.2.1 Degradation Models

The Weibull++ tool [44] incorporates several degradation models, including Linear, Exponential, Power, Logarithm, Gompertz, and Lloyd-Lipow.

During this study, only exponential, linear and logarithmic degradation models are used to analyse wall thickness measurement. The models are as follows:

$$\text{Linear: } x(t) = b + at, \quad (3.4)$$

$$\text{Exponential: } x(t) = be^{at}, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\text{Logarithmic: } x(t) = a \ln(t) + b, \quad (3.6)$$

where, $x(t)$ pipe wall thickness at time (t), a and b are model parameters respectively.

In this case, the corrosion data are ranked according to the most suitable distribution, and the best degradation model is selected.

3.3.3 Life Data Analysis

Life data are measured components of a system's life, it involves mapping statistical distributions to the measured data from a sample of the system, which is used to predict its reliability, likelihood of failure over time, the mean remaining life, failure rate, mean time to failure (MTTF), and confidence bound (Parameter Bounds). Simple steps to perform a life data analysis on the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool:

- **Step 1:** Assemble life data for the piping system. This can be transferred from the degradation analysis folio in Reliasoft Weibull++.
- **Step 2:** Choose a lifetime distribution model that describes the data and model the system's life.
- **Step 3:** Analyse the model to estimate the model parameters.
- **Step 4:** Develop plots and results that evaluate the life features of the piping system.
- **Step 5:** Apply the model parameters in the distribution model to mathematically compute reliability characteristics.
- **Step 6:** Use the reliability characteristics for Risk-Based Inspection (RBI).

The model parameters in a life data analysis are evaluated using Rank regression (RRX) on the data set. (x), Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE), Fisher Matrix (FM), Standard Ranking Method (SRM) used for estimating the failure time order, Median Ranking (MED).

3.3.3.1 Life Data Models

Researchers, Statisticians, mathematicians, and engineers have continuously developed and modified several life data models, including Weibull, Mixed-Weibull, Bayesian-Weibull, generalised Gamma, Gamma, Logistic, Loglogistic, and Gumbel, etc. For this study, only two such models are utilised: Gumbel and Weibull.

Gumbel Distribution

The Gumbel distribution is a Type I extreme-value distribution and exists in two forms: the minimum and maximum extreme-value distributions [55]. However, they are generally referred to as double exponentials due to their mathematical structure. The Gumbel extreme-value distribution is used to estimate the minimum/maximum wall thicknesses of a metal in a corrosive environment. Mathematically, the Gumbel model for reliability analysis is given below:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\beta} e^{-\frac{x-\mu}{\beta}} \cdot e^{-\frac{x-\mu}{\beta}}, \quad (3.7)$$

$$F(x) = e^{-e^{-x}}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$R(x) = 1 - e^{-e^{-x}}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$\lambda(x) = \frac{f(x)}{R(x)} = \frac{\frac{1}{\beta} e^{-\frac{x-\mu}{\beta}} \cdot e^{-\frac{x-\mu}{\beta}}}{1 - e^{-e^{-x}}}, \quad (3.10)$$

where $F(x)$ is Communitive Distribution Function (CDF) x is the estimated minimum wall thickness, u is the location parameter, β scale parameter. Mean Time to Failure (MTTF) or mean (μ_x) is given as $u + 0.5772/\beta$, where 0.5772 is Euler's constant. Standard Deviation (σ_x) is given as $\pi/(\beta\sqrt{6})$.

Weibull Distribution

Due to its efficiency, the Weibull distribution is widely used in asset integrity assessment and in predicting the allowable lifespan of a facility affected by corrosion. The Weibull distribution can be used to model a variety of life

behaviour systems, based on the values of the independent variable. The model is broken down mathematically as follows:

$$f(x) = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta} \right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta} \right)^{\beta}}, \quad (3.11)$$

$$f(x) \geq 0, \quad x \geq 0 \text{ or } \gamma, \beta > 0, \eta > 0, -\infty < \gamma < \infty,$$

$$R(x) = \int f(x) dx = e^{-\left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta} \right)^{\beta}}, \quad (3.12)$$

$$\lambda(x) = \frac{f(x)}{R(x)} = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta} \right)^{\beta-1}, \quad (3.13)$$

where, x is the random degradation value, $f(x)$ is the probability density function (PDF), $R(x)$ is the reliability function, $\lambda(x)$ is the failure rate function, β is the shape parameter, also known as the Weibull slope, η is the scale parameter, γ is the location parameter. The probability distribution function plot used to analyse and evaluate the results generated by this approach depends on the magnitude of the location parameter, β , and the scale parameter, η .

The Weibull distribution can take different forms depending on the number of parameters used in the analysis. The location parameter, γ , It is not often used, and this parameter's value can be set to zero. If this is the scenario, the model is a two-parameter (2P) Weibull distribution. In a scenario where a single parameter is used, the Weibull distribution is termed a one-parameter (1P) Weibull distribution. The condition of failure in a system analysed based on the Weibull distribution can be judged from the following condition:

$\beta < 1$ means corrosion reduces the thickness of the pipeline with time.

$\beta > 1$ insinuates that the pipeline thickness reduction due to corrosion increases over time.

$\beta = 1$ means the pipeline wall thickness reduction is constant over time.

Assumptions Made in the Study are as follows:

- The total length of the sampled material used in the Bx% Life (i.e., the time by which x% of the system will exceed allowable minimum thickness or fail) is made up of all straight paths excluding the bent sections. This is because the expression for the ordinate area was developed for straight paths only.
- The sampled width is assumed to be 25mm (1inch). Hence, in a sample length of 16m, 640 points are to be measured.
- Only minimum points from each block are adopted in the extreme value analysis (minimum extreme value approach).
- The data considered in the analysis are those measured from blocks inspected between 2003 and 2018.
- The measurement of wall thickness is assumed to commence after 1 year (365 days) of water injection system installation under steady operating conditions.
- Inspection durations are converted from years to days to achieve proper graph scaling.

Limitations Associated with the Data Used.

Given how measurements are obtained, some blocks had only two data points instead of four. However, due to inconsistent measurements and inspection intervals, the analysis results could be compromised, even though uncertainties are not considered.

3.4 Comparison between the API 570 Linear Extrapolation and Degradation Model Analysis Approach with the Reliasoft Weibull ++ Statistical tool.

Table 3.1 shows the relationship between inspection time and the level of degradation in a metal vessel with a critical degradation limit of 500mm. It can be visually ascertained from Table 3.1 that, even before the inspection, the degradation had exceeded the critical boundary. However, a leak had not ultimately occurred because the wall thickness had not gone below zero (0) mm. However, failure (bursting) is sure to occur if the system is under steady operating pressure. Hence, it is assumed that the system was not in operation when the wall thickness fell below the designated nominal wall thickness.

Table 3.1. Tank Wall Thickness Measurements

Inspection Time (hr)	Degradation (mm)	Critical Degradation (mm)
400	960	
600	890	500
800	850	
1000	810	

Alternatively, the API 570 Extrapolation Approach

The degradation can be plotted against their respective inspection time to predict future degradation and extrapolate the time when the system reaches the critical limit. See (Appendix B.1) for a graphical view of the extrapolation method.

Comment: The systems will exceed their critical degradation at exactly 1240hrs (0.14year) using the formula approach and approximately 2150 hours (0.25year) for the graphical approach, respectively. These are the times when the system is likely to start failing. However, the graphical approach gives a more preferred solution compared to the mathematical method.

Degradation Analysis

Refer to Appendix B.2 for the degradation-time graph developed in Reliasoft using an exponential model for the degradation data in Table 3.1.

Comment: From the analysis, the MTTF of the system is 15090 hrs (1.72 years). This is the time required for the degradation to reach a thickness of 500 mm.

Summary

Compared to the Weibull++ tool, it provides more time before inspection and prevents expenses that may result from untimely inspection, maintenance, or repair timing. Also, the graph in Appendix B.1 shows that corrosion in the system is non-linear, which is more realistic than the API 570 approach, which treats corrosion as a linear variable. It is also worth noting that if the MTTF is extensive, as estimated in the degradation analysis, failure can be intermediate, which is detrimental to the system. However, the MTTF value for the API 570 approach is lower than that for the software, as it mainly depends on the amount of available data [56]. Hence, where the data are sufficient, the results produced by both methods are reliable. However, the point-to-point approach has no capacity to minimise the level of uncertainties in the inspection data.

Chapter 4: Residual life estimation. Life data, Degradation model applications, and Point-to-Point Analysis.

Keeping the study's objective in mind, this chapter will use wall thickness measurement data to perform life data and degradation analysis in the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool. Also, the commonly used API 570 Point-to-Point extrapolation and API 510 residual-life estimation corroded-metal vessel methods will be analysed using Eq. (3.1-3.3), with similar data from Table C.1 of the Appendix. To justify the research, the results from the different approaches will be compared in this section. The advantages and disadvantages of each approach will be summarised to help users make the best decision and select the most convenient method for studying a corroded piping system.

4.1 Case study: Piping in an oil and gas water injection system.

The piping of a water injection system is expanded to distribute water from the pump to the reservoir. Reservoirs after several years of production tend to have reduced pressure or yields, and a standard method of enhancing oil recovery in such reservoirs is injecting water, fresh/seawater, which raises the crude oil to the top layer of the reservoir. Notwithstanding, seawater has been shown to accelerate corrosion of the water-injection piping system. In some cases, additives are added to water to reduce corrosion rates and seal leaks, yet the problem persists. Table C.1 contains the wall thickness measurements for different years of inspection used in the API 570 extrapolation and degradation model analysis methods.

4.2 Point-to-Point Analysis

The point-to-point analysis involves collecting piping wall thickness measurements at different times during operation, plotting the degradation over time using a semi-quantitative linear method, and extrapolating to the time when the degradation reaches or exceeds the defined critical wall thickness.

Table 4.1: API510 Semi-Quantitative Analysis of Residual Life of Corroded Piping System.

Parameters	Sub-System 01	Sub-System 02	Sub-System 03	Sub-System 03
T_{First} (mm)	22.0000	22.0000	22.0000	22.0000
$T_{Previous}$ (mm)	13.5000	13.3000	14.3600	16.9100
T_{Last} (mm)	13.2000	13.1000	13.9300	16.5700
STCR (mm/Day)	0.0008	0.0005	0.0012	0.0009
LTCR (mm/Day)	0.0016	0.0016	0.0015	0.0010
CR	0.0016	0.0016	0.0015	0.0010
Residual Life (Days)	137	74	644	3619

Tables 4.1 and 4.2 show the residual life and time-to-failure results for both the API 570 linear regression methodology and the API 510 semi-quantitative equation approaches. The estimated residual life computed from semi-quantitative Eq. (3.1-3.3) in Table 4.2 shows that failure can occur at an early age of the piping system. The piping wall thickness measurement from Table C.1 was plotted against the inspection time, and a straight line was extrapolated to forecast the time when the wall thickness reduces to 12.98mm for all four (4) sub-systems.

Table 4.2 Time to Failure Analysis for Corroded Piping System from Point-to-Point Method.

Systems	Sub-System 01	Sub-System 02	Sub-System 03	Sub-System 04
Time to Fail (Days)	4989	6158	5914	8634

Comparing the results in Tables 4.1 and 4.2 shows that the API 570 approach yields a result closer to that obtained using the linear degradation model in the Reliasoft Statistical tool. Although the values in Table 4.2 are time-to-failure values, if any of them are used to subtract half the system's year (183 days), the least residual life computed by the API 570 approach is still far higher than that calculated by API 510. Appendices (D.1-D4) give a graphical explanation of the API 570 extrapolation method used to obtain results in Table 4.2.

4.3 Degradation Model Analysis

It is a significant concern for an asset manager to determine the modes and times of failure of a facility. Degradation analysis was performed on data from four sub-systems to estimate the failure time of four (4) sub-piping systems, and it shows that wall thickness degradation follows a linear distribution, indicating the linkage between wall thickness reduction and failure time. Nevertheless, the other degradation models mentioned in section (3.3.2.1) can also be applied in the analysis, and the software automatically selects the most suitable one based on the magnitude of the correlation coefficient and the likelihood value. The linear model is ranked as the best for the analysis; hence, it has been adopted. However, a linear model is a straightforward approach and can be used to model several forms of deterioration in engineering materials [57]. Using Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Analysis Tools, the model parameters a (slope) and b (intercept) are established as shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3. Linear Degradation Model Parameters

Linear Degradation Analysis				
Parameters				
Unit ID	Parameter a	Std - a	Parameter b	Std - b
Sub-System 01 Unit ID 1 Wall Thickness	-0.001922	0.000098	23.056384	0.316054
Sub-System 02 Unit ID 2 Wall Thickness	-0.001741	0.000137	23.622554	0.441797
Sub-System 03 Unit ID 3 Wall Thickness	-0.00147	0.000024	21.704802	0.078355
Sub-System 04 Unit ID 4 Wall Thickness	-0.001044	0.000013	22.197823	0.04278

Table 4.4. Extrapolated time to failure results from the Linear Degradation Model

Systems	Time to Fail (Days)
Sub-System 01	5255
Sub-System 02	6093
Sub-System 03	5942

Applying the model parameters in Eq. (3.4), the mean time to failure in Table 4.4 can be evaluated manually. In this study, failure is defined as the point at which the wall thickness reaches 12.98mm. Therefore, the time-to-failure for each subsystem can be directly estimated from the linear or logarithmic degradation-time graphs in Fig. 4.1 and 4.2. The degradation time graph shows that the system starts failing after the various degradation lines intersect the extensive horizontal pink line (critical). Table 4.4 presents the time-to-failure for each subsystem analysed.

Figure 4.1. Degradation Time Graph (Linear)

Figure 4.2. Degradation Time Graph (Logarithm)

Figure 4.3. Residual Life and Degradation Time Graph (Linear)

In an asset management process, it is necessary to estimate residual life to evaluate a system's remaining life after years of steady operation. Appropriate maintenance and preventive measures can be implemented based on the estimated residual life to prevent the system from severe hazards. A conceptual estimation of the residual life of a sub-piping system (Sub-system 01) is found in Fig. 4.3. The residual life is estimated as the difference between the anticipated day of failure and the current day the system is in steady operation ($5255 - 1201 = 4054$ days).

The following action is to transfer the degradation model into a life data analysis using a 2P-Weibull distribution to predict the system's reliability properties, if all subsystems undergo a similar failure process.

4.4 Life Data Analysis

The time-to-failure of the respective subsystems in Table 4.4 was transferred from the degradation model in Section 4.3 using the sophisticated nature of the Reliasoft tool. However, similar failure times can still be obtained for the systems if they are analysed directly using life data analysis, but that would be time-consuming.

Table 4.5. Life Data Analysis of Failure Time

State F or S	Time to F (Day)	Unit ID	Distribution Parameters Reliasoft Weibull++
F	5242	Sub-System 01	
F	6113	Sub-System 02	$\beta = 5.0560, \eta (\text{day}) = 7036.272$
F	5935	Sub-System 03	LK Value = -34.781, $\rho = 0.887571$
F	8897	Sub-System 04	

It is worth noting that, regardless of the value of β , the time-to-failure distribution does not deviate from the assumption that system degradation is random. However, in real engineering conditions, the failure time is dependent on the amount of data available for the Weibull analysis. Irrespective of that, engineering knowledge should be used to validate statistical analysis, even though it concerns only the amount of data available for study, not the behaviour of the system. Table 4.5 shows the values of the 2P-Weibull model parameters, shape parameter β and scale parameter η , equal to 5.0560 and 7036.2721, respectively, as analysed using the Reliasoft tool. The correlation coefficient is greater than 70%, indicating that the Weibull model explains the system's deterioration well. The life data analysis predicts that four (4) of the systems will fail and none will survive at a specific time in service, as shown in column two (2) of Table 4.5.

4.4.1 Comparison between Reliasoft Weibull++ and Relyence Weibull Life Data Analysis

To avoid a hasty conclusion on the efficacy and suitability of the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool for analysing a corroded piping system, a similar time-to-failure value from column 2 of Table 4.6 was applied in a different computer-aided reliability analysis tool, Relyence. A quick comparison of Reliasoft Weibull++ and Relyence Weibull 2P distribution parameters is presented in Table 4.6 below. A fair judgement will be made by selecting the method with the highest correlation coefficient (i.e., greater than or approximately equal to 1.0) for analysing the data for this project.

From Table 4.6, it indicates that the Beta (β) values for both Reliasoft Weibull++ and Relyence Weibull Life Data Analysis are greater than 1.0. In a case where the reliability engineer is not highly skilled, this would be alarming; in an analytical sense, it does not affect the reliability analysis but indicates the failure condition. However, for Beta > 1.0, the dataset shows low variation.

And if the Beta is greater than 1.0 and the Eta (η) is relatively high, the analysis result is valid. The high Beta value would enhance the effectiveness of precautionary maintenance in the system. According to section (3.3.3.1), the Beta values from the two software indicate that the piping degradation increases over time. It is worth noting that a high Beta value yields an unreasonable slope, which can leave the analyst confused when judging by the visual interpretation of the probability plots. Analysing the set of failure times in column two (2) of Table 4.6 based on ranked regression analysis for both software, and comparing the correlation coefficient (ρ) produced by both computer tools, it can be concluded that the Relyence Weibull tool gives a better fit for the sets of wall thickness data in Table C.1.

Table 4.6. Life Data Analysis Result for Reliasoft Weibull++ and Relyence Weibull.

State F or S	Time to F (Day)	Unit ID	2P-Weibull Distribution Parameters	
			Reliasoft Weibull++	Relyence Weibull
F	5242	Sub-System 01		
F	6113	Sub-System 02	$\beta = 5.0560, \eta \text{ (day)} = 7036.272$	$\beta = 3.9827, \eta \text{ (day)} = 7217.6284$
F	5935	Sub-System 03	LK Value = -34.781, $\rho = 0.887571$	$\rho^2 = 0.788218, \rho = 0.887817$
F	8897	Sub-System 04		

Comparing the PDF plots in Fig. 4.4 and 4.5, generated from Reliasoft and Relyence tools respectively, the data skips away from the mean in the Relyence PDF plot. At the same time, they fall close (clusters) to the mean in the Reliasoft PDF plot, though this variation is insignificant, and shows that the PDFs from both software are symmetrically skewed.

The other reliability plots for life Relyence life data analysis are shown in Appendices (E.1-E.4), while those of Reliasoft are found in Appendices (E.5-E.8).

Figure 4.4. Probability Density Function for the Reliasoft Weibull++ software tool.

Considering the model parameters, the reliability analysis can be conducted by simple substitution in $R(t) = \int f(x)dx = e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\beta}$, to estimate the reliability of the piping system at a given time and subtract the result from one (1), to subsequently evaluate the probability of a leak occurring in the piping. Based on life data analysis, piping reliability can be assessed at any point in time during operation to support decision-making on maintenance, repair, or inspection of the water injection piping. Table 4.7 presents the results from Reliasoft statistical software testing the integrity of the piping system after 7300 days (20 years) of steady operation, using historical data (wall thickness reduction) in Table C.1.

Corroded Water Injection Piping System Life Data Analysis.

Figure 4.5. Probability Density Function (PDF) for Relyence Weibull software tool.

Table 4.7. Reliability Characteristics of the Water Injection Piping System

Characteristics	Value
Reliability R (7300)	0.3000
Probability of Failure Pf (7300)	0.7000
Reliable Life t(R=0.85) (Day)	4912
B10% (Day)	4509
MTTF/Mean Life (Day)	6465
Mean Remaining Life (Day)	823
Failure Rate (failures/mm)	0.000834/day

4.4.2 Reliability Analysis

The probability plot, reliability $R(t)$, unreliability $U(t)$, and failure rate $\lambda(t)$ enable comparative analysis. The reliability quantities can be evaluated from their graphs generated in Appendix (E.5-E.8). Equation (11) is derived from the convergence of the order of piping wall thickness measurements. The form of the distribution is defined by how this set of data converges, and the distribution function determines the thickness measurements that depend on it. To ensure the piping is 85% safer, the system should be checked after 4912 days of steady operation. From Table 4.7, the piping system's reliability after 7300 days (20 years) of operation is critically below 50%, with a 70% probability of failure; therefore, the piping is conditionally rated with a likelihood of loss of containment. The failure rate graph in Appendix (E.8) indicates that failures in the corroded piping increase over time, consistent with the bathtub curve. Given the increasing failures, the developed failure rate graph is valid. It describes a typical corrosion-deterioration mechanism for the piping system, where degradation increases in parallel with the corrosion rate. In this case, the system is expected to undergo improvement to achieve the required reliability; otherwise, a failure is expected in the coming days, which will be more expensive than the maintenance.

4.4.3 Percentile Life

In the Reliasoft tool, B(x)-Life is used to express the component or system's percentile failure rate and estimate the time to a given level of deterioration (failure) with a given level of confidence. The percentile life (upper and lower bounds) can also be used to establish a guarantee of a system's performance or condition. For example, in Table 4.7 above, at 4509 days (12.4years), 10% (B(x)-10%) of the piping system has already failed, hence, the system is living on 90% of its lifespan from that time upwards. The estimated B(x)-Life can serve as a background against which an asset manager makes their decision, ensuring the system's integrity is reliable at all times of operation. Table 4.8 shows the percentile life of the four sub-systems analysed.

Statistically, based on historical data on wall thickness measurements (Table 4.8), the system's integrity can be compromised in a cost-saving situation. Assuming the piping system is defined to burst when 75% of the wall thickness has been lost to corrosion, the asset manager can determine from the analysis the time at which this hazard will occur. However, in other methods, such as the Point-to-Point, no room is provided for such analysis, and the system is considered failed whenever it reaches the defined critical point, regardless of whether it has entirely failed, rendering the process not cost-effective. Also, the percentile life of a system depends on the network time (series or parallel), which influences the failure rate, and as the system ages, it deteriorates, as shown in Fig. 4.1.

Table 4.8. Percentile Life of Piping Sub-System corresponding Upper and Lower 90 % Confidence Bounds

X-Life (%)	Time to failure (Days)		
	90% Lower Bound	Actual B(x)-Life	90% Upper Bound
5	2461	3910	6213
10	3075	4509	6611
25	4169	5500	7255
50 (mean life)	5365	6545	7983

These values in Table 4.8 aid the asset manager in setting a guarantee for the system. Thus, given the confidence bound, we are 90% confident that half of the wall thickness has been lost after 6545 days of operation. But in a mild case (lower bound), where the corrosion is not rapid, it might be after 5365 days; at worst (upper bound), 7983 days, where the corrosion is considered extreme.

4.4.5 Model Fitting

To obtain a perfect statistical plot, the data should be independent of uncertainties to some extent. In this study, the data set was inconsistent, so only data measured in 2017 for different CMLs were used in the extreme value analysis due to their greater conformity. Table C.3 is the combination of wall thickness data from Table C.2, arranged in ascending order and termed as “general piping system”. Model fitting is a system of assessing the suitability of a statistical model in justifying the behaviour of system’s failure mechanism and to show the level of relationship between the model and the data. Appendices (F.1 and F.2) give plots of probability density function (f(t)) against the respective wall thicknesses for 2P-Weibull and 2P-Gumbel distributions, respectively. These plots show that the PDFs for Area-E from Weibull and Gumbel distributions are symmetrically skewed, whereas the other areas are slightly skewed to the right by visual inspection.

The statistical test used to assess whether a model describes the data is known as the Goodness-of-Fit test. Skewness and percentile methods are among the earliest approaches for evaluating a model's fitness for a given data set [58]. However, maximum likelihood estimation is one of the most widely used approaches for assessing goodness-of-fit. This study has based its judgement on the maximum likelihood and correlation coefficient, considering the CML that developed the best goodness-of-fit characteristics (Area-E). However, other methods are available for evaluating a model's fitness on a given dataset [44, 59]. Table 4.9 presents the results from the analysis of Weibull++ statistical software for the Gumbel and Weibull distributions of different CML. The distributions have been discussed in Chapter 3, and several literatures have been referenced in Chapter 2 on the statistical application of these distributions.

Table 4.9. 2P-Weibull Distribution parameters

CMLs	Distribution Parameters							
	2P-Gumbel Probability Distribution				2P-Weibull Probability Distribution			
	Shape Parameter μ	Scale Parameter σ	LK	ρ	β	η	LK	ρ
Area-A	17.9961	0.6662	-7.0121	0.98	26.2145	17.9896	-7.0675	0.98

CMLs	Distribution Parameters							
	2P-Gumbel Probability Distribution			2P-Weibull Probability Distribution				
	Shape Parameter μ	Scale Parameter σ	LK	ρ	β	η	LK	ρ
Area-B	19.2788	1.3341	-17.7268	0.82	14.3102	19.2046	-16.4710	0.84
Area-C	17.8156	0.5080	-4.8833	0.96	34.0419	17.8132	-4.9729	0.95
Area-D	18.2527	0.4967	-5.3013	0.98	36.0630	18.2485	-5.2898	0.98
Area-E	15.4990	0.2226	0.4916	1.00	68.9474	15.4980	0.4914	1.00
General System	17.7425	0.9069	-42.7080	0.97	18.5260	17.7255	-43.1175	0.97

Probability plot in Figs. 4.6 and 4.7 stand as a visual inspection mechanism to assess the model fitness. This approach can be erroneous, given the level of understanding and the analyst's optical condition. The Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical software can help reduce the difficulty of visual analysis of probability plots when making decisions by automatically estimating the correlation coefficient and maximum likelihood values. With reference to the maximum likelihood and coefficient of correlation for Area-E, regardless of the goodness-of-fit of the 2P-Weibull distribution, the model that best describes the system is the Gumbel distribution, with a maximum likelihood of 0.4916 and a coefficient of correlation of 1.00. Not minding the perfect quality of the Weibull distribution with a coefficient of correlation equal to that of the Gumbel model, although it possesses a maximum likelihood of 0.041% less. The Gumbel distribution is a better model for the distribution of minimum extreme values [37]. Appendices (G.1-G.3) present a comparative graph of the fitness of the Gumbel and Weibull distributions to a set of wall thickness measurements in Table C.3. The extreme-value distribution parameters obtained from the Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical software depend on the system's failure. They can thus be used for reliability analysis using Equ. (3.7-3.13). A quick example could be defining the level of degradation and computing the system's properties, such as reliability, hazard function, and probability of failure, for the general piping system.

Consider the distribution parameter (β, η) for the general system estimated from the Weibull distribution and obtain the reliability, hazard function, and probability of failure at a wall thickness equal to 12.98mm (critical degradation). Given that for the General system, $\beta = 18.5260, \gamma = 0, \eta = 17.7255, x = 12.98$,

Reliability:

$$R(x) = \int f(x)dx = e^{-\left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta} = 0.9969$$

Probability of Failure:

$$Pf(x) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta} = 0.0031$$

Hazard Function:

$$\lambda(x) = \frac{f(x)}{R(x)} = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\eta}\right)^{\beta-1} = 0.007116$$

Figure 4.6. Gumbel Probability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.

Figure 4.7. Weibull Probability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.

The hazard function is the instantaneous rate of failure over time and can be adequately modelled using the Weibull distribution to predict the wearout of a piping surface. With a reliability of approximately 1.00, the piping system still has sufficient integrity to maintain its performance standard, and the failure is irrelevant at this wall thickness. Recall that the failure starts when the wall thickness exceeds the critical degradation. However, the extreme value approach does not require wall thickness measurement at different years, unlike the API 510 method. It would be adequate to inspect the piping system once a year, and to use the minimum or maximum wall thicknesses from each CML to analyse the entire system and predict where failure is certain to occur.

Figure 4.8. Gumbel Reliability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.

Figure 4.9. Weibull Reliability Plot for Wall Thickness Reliasoft Weibull++ Statistical Software.

Table 4.10. Gumbel Extreme Value Estimation of Minimum Wall Thickness with Reliasoft Weibull++

CMLs	Area of CMLs (N)	Ordinate	BX% Life	Minimum Thickness x at 1-Sided Lower Bound of 90% Confidence Level	Minimum Thickness x (mm)	Probability of Failure at Minimum Thickness x	One-Sided Upper Bound Probability of Failure at Minimum Thickness x
Area-A	2185	0.04575	B0.04575% Life	9.8054	12.87	0.00445	0.04465
Area-B	2241	0.04460	B0.04460% Life	6.2887	8.99	0.000447	0.00337
Area-C	2176	0.04594	B0.04594% Life	11.0711	13.91	0.000458	0.01159
Area-D	2228	0.04486	B0.04486% Life	12.6540	14.42	0.000445	0.01564
Area-E	1911	0.05230	B0.05230% Life	12.9828	13.82	0.000133	0.007970
General System	10741	0.00931	B0.00931% Life	7.400	9.32	0.0000	0.00005

Applying the Gumbel extreme value to estimate the minimum wall thickness, the different CMLs by computing the ordinate in column three (3) of Table 4.10 using Eq. (8). The minimum wall thickness for the sampled water injection piping system can be obtained from Area-B with a minimum thickness of 8.99mm, and a One-sided 90% lower confidence level of 6.2887mm. Whereas, the minimum wall thickness of the general system is 9.32mm, and the one-sided 90% lower confidence level is 7.40mm. The probability of the system failing when the minimum wall thickness is 8.99mm increases rapidly and can be computed mathematically from Eq. (3.12), incorporating the Gumbel parameters in Table 4.10. However, the Weibull++ software, which offers several notable features, can be used to estimate the probability of system failure and to specify upper or lower confidence limits for the system's likelihood of failure. The probability of leakage in Area-B when the piping wall thickness reduces to zero is approximately 0.45%. The one-sided 90% upper confidence limit for this probability is approximately 4.5%. This can be attributed to uncertainties in the data and its size.

Table 4.11. Comparison of Time to Failure (Day) for Point-to-Point vs Life Data Analysis

Systems	Point-to-Point	Life Data Analysis
Sub-System 01	4989	5292
Sub-System 02	6158	6113
Sub-System 03	5914	5965
Sub-System 04	8634	8897

To track a piping system's performance, asset managers use approaches to define its reliability. Mean Time to Failure is one such approach used to assess system reliability, although it does not provide sufficient information to determine the system's integrity level. The MTTF, which in most cases has been derived by dividing the system's total operating time by the total number of failures in the subsystems. This definition is only suitable when the data used to describe the system follows an exponential distribution, and the failure rate is constant throughout the system's operational time. But, where the case is different, it becomes erroneous to apply such a definition. The data set used in this analysis does not follow an exponential distribution; instead, it is best described by a linear distribution. However, if the MTTF is

linked to a confidence level, it is considered a welcome development, a more versatile and robust metric for describing a product's reliability. The MTTF estimated with Weibull++ in Table 4.11, column three (3), appears more desirable, as it allows the MTTF to be obtained at various confidence levels and bounds (Two-Sided, Both One-Sided, Upper-One Sided, Lower One-Sided), etc.

Table 4.11 shows four different times-to-failure for their respective components, analysed using two approaches: API 570 Point-to-Point and Weibull++ life data analysis. The result shows that when the subsystems are analysed using the API 570 approach, the time to failure is shorter than in life data analysis. Hence, failure is likely to occur in the subsystem earlier than supposed. Notwithstanding, the life data approach yields the most significant failure time, which can be misleading when failure occurs earlier than estimated, leading to loss of containment. In a real-time practice, the engineer would make his decision on the best MTTF based on his technical knowledge of the studied system or from historical failures of similar facilities.

A shorter MTTF indicates that the system will often experience downtime (MTTR) and trouble more quickly. It will also be noted that the system's failure can occur in two stages: partial and total. Which means a system can reach its MTTF and still produce results (partial failure). Also, the same system can achieve its MTTF and stop functioning or develop a failure that stops operation (total failure). Therefore, the validity of an MTTF requires substantial meaningful data [60]. The result of this analysis kow-tows to that in [61]: it shows that the failure times evaluated from the degradation model are greater than those estimated using the API 510 Pressure Vessel Inspection Code approach.

4.5 Preferences and Limitations of the Methods used in Estimating Residual Wall Thickness and Life of Oil and Gas Piping.

Preference for the point-to-point method

The distinct advantage of this approach is its ease of application to an entire pipeline or collection of pipelines, as well as its ability to be understood by people without an engineering background.

Limitations of the Point-to-Point Method

The deterministic approach may often, but not entirely, be linked to inaccuracies in the input data. Notably, the inability to handle uncertainties in input data is a limiting factor for this approach. This method can only be used for uniform corrosion and is unsuitable for non-uniform corrosion. The pipeline operator is subject to risk in field corrosion defect measurement. The technique requires a relatively large number of inspection data to produce an approximate result if possible [62]. The method does not create room for a probabilistic view. It can be inaccurate and misleading; however, the literature suggests that corrosion degradation is rarely linear. Hence, the estimate is too optimistic; there is a danger of failure and loss of containment. If it is too conservative, there is a risk of replacing piping too early or when it does not need to be replaced, resulting in lost production (revenue) and increased costs.

Preference of the Statistical Extreme Value Method

Statistical methodology for corrosion analysis is appropriate when gathering inspection data is hindered by limited access, especially within the pipeline. Since a portion can be used to sample the entire pipeline network, this approach is efficient, cost-effective and easy to apply. The application of a statistical approach, such as extreme value analysis, provides robust predictions of the pipeline system's future behaviour and gives operators a better understanding of the

actual line condition. The extreme-value statistical approach reduces uncertainty in inspection data by accounting for the minimum and maximum values. The statistical approach, such as extreme value analysis, can be adopted when data points are inadequate yet still yield dependable, conservative results.

This method offers a probabilistic perspective on the current condition, considering the whole line/system. This approach requires high-quality data, although it can minimise uncertainties in the dataset.

Limitations of the Statistical Extreme Value Method

The area extrapolation statistical approach does not account for confidence limits when evaluating the minimum pipe wall thickness. Neither does it generate a distribution of the minimum wall thickness required to analyse the system's reliability [2]. Also, insufficient data could compromise the reliability of the results obtained with this approach.

Needs more specialists in statistical and probability modelling; as a result, it is complicated for people with a low engineering background, which in turn hinders its application. According to the UK HSE report's recommendations, the statistical method would be more accurate if specialist tools, such as the Reliasoft tool, were used, enabling many measurements to be compared quickly. But most of these specialist tools require a subscription (financial payment). Although it can be done in Excel, it requires a highly skilled analyst with the knowledge to perform tasks accurately. However, it could be done in Excel if analysts have the right skills and expertise; I would recommend specialist software for quickly comparing many measurements.

Preference of the Probabilistic Method

The use of a probabilistic approach yields results closer to reality by avoiding excessive conservatism, defines a standard level of reliability for the pipeline system, and enables the integration of parameters to evaluate failure risk. The method is suitable for high-dimensional problems and complex computations because it combines simple computer programming, such as Monte Carlo Simulation, with high efficiency and the ability to moderate uncertainties in inspection data. This approach can be used to estimate the time to failure of a pipeline based on the criticality of metal losses. It provides a clear understanding of the system's condition and allows the pipeline operator to act when necessary.

Limitations of the Probabilistic Method

Developing a model that incorporates all parameters influencing pipeline failure could be complex and require sophisticated analytical tools. Therefore, these tools are sometimes unavailable.

Preference of the Degradable Parametric models

A non-degradable corrosion model can be applied to reduce epistemic uncertainty [63, 64]. The models are suitable for performing probabilistic assertions to estimate the extent of pipeline failure and potential leak size based on statistics or observations [65].

Limitations of Degradable Parametric models

This approach requires more mathematical skill and knowledge than point-to-point, and it does not allow parts of the system to be measured. A lack of historical data can be a problem with this method. However, this approach requires

specialist software; while it can be done in Excel, there is a risk of errors if carried out by people without the right knowledge of degradation modelling.

The disadvantages of ANNs include the time it takes to run models and the high cost of data collection. Those are the reasons this model was applied only for academic research. The Markov approach is somewhat tedious in real-world practice and requires lengthy computations, leading to cumbersome calculations and large amounts of data [66-69]. This is the same case for pipeline systems in [63]. A limitation of a Bayesian Network model used in corrosion analysis is the complexity of evaluating the conditional probability tables, which can be mitigated through data training. However, most industries do not account for failure frequencies or pipeline data [70]. Several such models require a high level of mathematical knowledge to apply, and a lack of computational power has also limited their use. It was observed in [71] that the power law is a suitable means of studying corrosion; however, it has limitations in handling uncertainties in corrosion data. Suleiman et al [72] also detected the poor treatment of uncertainties in the use of a linear regression model for corrosion analysis. This is in accordance with the findings in [73].

Chapter 5 Conclusions and Recommendations.

5.1 Conclusion

In fact, the rate of accidents in the oil and gas industry has continued to decrease compared to earlier decades. Notwithstanding, the industry is working tirelessly to prevent situations that may lead to accidents within the oil and gas industry, as these accidents carry severe consequences, including high numbers of deaths, financial losses, environmental degradation, and reputational damage, unlike those in other sectors. Therefore, it has been deemed necessary by regulatory bodies that all operators within the oil and gas industry must maintain a high level of safety and ascertain the integrity of their assets at all times in operation to ensure that accidents such as piping failure that may lead to loss of containment are as low as reasonably practicable (ALARP).

During the safeguarding of an engineering system through maintenance or repair, an operator must consider the process's cost-effectiveness and ensure it does not reduce the system's efficiency afterwards. To study the residual life (remaining wall thickness) of a critical corroded piping component in a water injection system, various methodologies have been critically reviewed, with their benefits and constraints noted. A comparative analysis has been conducted on point-to-point methods, non-destructive parametric degradation models, and statistical minimum-extreme-value distribution methods for estimating wall thickness using real data. Considering the problems highlighted by the UK HSE [2], which is the application of a computer-aided tool and statistical Extreme Value Analysis (EVA) in predicting future wall thickness of a corroded facility, real data were applied in the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool to perform reliability analysis and estimate the minimum wall thickness on a piping surface hit by corrosion.

The following conclusions have been drawn from the literature reviews and results obtained in the project:

The Extreme Value Analysis has proven to be a more sophisticated and desirable approach than the API 570 Point-to-Point and parametric degradation models. However, to comprehend the mechanism of a piping system's residual life, adequate, high-quality historical failure data is required for accurate prediction. Nevertheless, the estimated MTTF of the piping system is not conclusive or unconditional; therefore, it is most often the responsibility of the asset integrity engineer to define the time-to-failure based on experience or records of past failures. However, applying the rule of thumb is detrimental to making critical decisions in the engineering industry. This level of integrity is developed based on the company's risk perception and working standards. In practice, there should be a risk criterion that defines a satisfactory, practical level of safety for the system. The Reliasoft tool, as recommended by API 570 [1], provides cost savings and an absolute reliability analysis compared to the API 570 method of estimating residual life. In the Reliasoft Weibull++ statistical tool, several system functions can be evaluated, unlike the API 570 approach, which only estimates residual life. The API 570 approach is not cost-effective and requires adequate data to arrive at an accurate solution.

It is a common approach in asset management and inspection processes to continuously conduct Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) on a corroded metal to evaluate the remaining wall thickness rather than applying a probabilistic, extreme-value, or degradation model. Although conducting NDT would provide an integrity engineer with vital details about the system, it is not cost-effective. It requires more time and system shutdowns, which may lead to production losses. Given the cost and efficiency of the extreme value approach, which requires only minimum/maximum wall thicknesses from a single inspection, it is the best method for estimating residual wall thickness in corroded piping. In section 1 of this study, it was argued that the industry has neglected the extreme value approach due to its complexity. Still, the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool can help ease the difficulties encountered when using it. Aside from Reliasoft

Weibull++, other computer-aided tools can be used to analyse corrosion data and estimate the residual life of the corroded system. However, none of these tools has the capacity of the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool for assessing the minimum wall thickness using Eq. 8.

5.2 Recommendations for Further Studies.

The accuracy of this study depends on the quality of the data used; incorporating data uncertainties into the analysis would help validate the project's results. Therefore, estimating the residual life of a corroded piping material with quality data using the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool is a welcome development. The rate of corrosion is dependent on the variability of influencing factors such as the environment where the piping is situated, material properties of piping, the fluid contained in the pipe, the temperature of the fluid, pressure in the piping system, level of usage, age of the system, etc., Hence, developing a non-homogenous probabilistic model to estimate the probability of piping failure and comparing results with that calculated from Reliasoft Weibull++ would help in ensuring the safety of an oil and gas piping system. Based on the estimated likelihood of failure from the limit-state function probabilistic model, a Quantitative Risk Analysis (QRA) should be conducted to determine the severity of the piping system failing at a time in service. In evaluating minimum wall thickness expected to occur in a thickness monitoring location during pipe inspection, it would be appreciated that while using the Reliasoft Weibull++, specific equations should be developed for all extreme value distributions instead of generally using the Gumbel ordinate in Eq. 8. Also, a comparison should be conducted as to which of the equations produces a more conservative ordinate. To do away with the application of the rule of thumb, the level of deterioration in the piping system should be ascertained by the results from the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool, such as failure probability, reliability, mean remaining life, reliable life, failure rate, MTTF, time to failure and percentile life, which should serve as a guide. Finally, given the MTTF computed across the different approaches, it is recommended that the MTTF estimated by the Reliasoft Weibull++ tool not be used directly. Hence, engineering knowledge is required to select the most cost-effective MTTF.

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APPENDIX

A Degradation Wizard on Reliasoft Weibull++.

Figure A.1. Weibull ++ Degradation Model Wizard Analysis.

Figure A.2. Model Ranked by Weibull ++ Degradation Model Wizard tool.

B. Comparative analysis of API 570 Point-to-Point Extrapolation and Degradation Analysis.

Figure B.1. Degradation vs Time graph of a Point-to-Point Method

Figure B.2. Degradation-Time graph

C.1. Water Injection Wall thickness Estimation

Table C.1. Piping Wall Thickness Measurements

Time of Inspection (Days)	Sub-System 01	Sub-System 02	Sub-System 03	Sub-System 04
1	22	22	22	22
365	21.9	22	21.34	21.99
730	21.8	21.9	20.70	21.55
1095	21.5	21.9	20.08	21.12
1460	21.3	21.7	19.48	20.70
1825	19.8	21.5	18.89	20.28
2190	19	20.5	18.33	19.88
2555	18.5	20	17.78	19.48
2920	18.2	19	17.24	19.09
3285	16.8	18.5	16.73	18.71
3650	15	18	16.22	18.33
4015	14.7	17.6	15.74	17.97
4380	14	16	15.26	17.61
4745	13.5	14.7	14.81	17.26
5110	13.5	13.3	14.36	16.91
5475	13.2	13.1	13.93	16.57

Table C.2. Life Data Analysis for Minimum Wall Thickness extracted from each Inspected Area in year 2017

Minimum Wall Thicknesses Measurement (mm) at different CMLs for year 2017 Inspection				
Area A	Area B	Area C	Area D	Area E
16.5	16.7	17.4	17.1	15
16.9	17.8	17.5	17.7	15.2
17.4	18	16.4	17.8	15.3
18	18.1	17.6	18	15.4
18.1	18.6	17.9	18.1	15.5
18.3	18.7	18	18.6	15.6

Table C.3. Life Data Analysis for Minimum Wall Thickness of the General Piping System Inspected in year 2017

Extreme Minimum Wall Thickness (mm) from the General System
15, 15.2, 15.3, 15.4, 15.5, 15.6, 16.4, 16.5, 16.7, 16.9, 17.1, 17.4, 17.4, 17.5, 17.6, 17.7, 17.8, 17.9, 18 18.1, 18.3, 18.6, 18.6, 18.7

D. API 570 Point-to-Point Analysis

Figure D.1. Extrapolation of time to failure of Sub-System 01

Figure D.2. Extrapolation of time to failure of Sub-System 02

Figure D.3. Extrapolation of time to failure of Sub-System 03

Figure D.4. Extrapolation of time to failure of Sub-System 04

E. Life Data Analysis

Relyence Weibull Plots

Corroded Water Injection Piping System Life Data Analysis.

Failure Rate vs Time

Figure E.1. Failure Rate plot for Relyence Life Data Analysis

Corroded Water Injection Piping System Life Data Analysis.

Probability

Figure E.2. Probability plot for Relyence Life Data Analysis

Corroded Water Injection Piping System Life Data Analysis.

Reliability vs Time

Figure E.3. Reliability plot for Relyence Life Data Analysis

Corroded Water Injection Piping System Life Data Analysis.

Unreliability vs Time

Figure E.4. Unreliability plot for Relyence Life Data Analysis

Figure E.5. Probability Plot for Life data Analysis of the general system

Figure E.6. Reliability plot for Life data Analysis of the general system

Figure E.7. Unreliability plot for Life data Analysis of the general system

Figure E.8. Failure Rate curve for Life data Analysis of the general system

F. Curve Fitting

Figure F.1. Comparison of Extreme Values 2P-Weibull PDF of Individual Areas

Figure F.2. Comparison of Extreme Values 2P-Gumbel PDF of Individual Areas

G. Comparison between Weibull and Gumbel Distribution.

Figure G.1. Comparison of Extreme Values 2P-Weibull and 2P-Gumbel PDF for Area-E

Figure G.2. Comparison of Extreme Values 2P-Weibull and 2P-Gumbel Reliability Plot for Area-E

Figure G.3. Comparison of Extreme Values 2P-Weibull and 2P-Gumbel Unreliability Plot for Area-E.